

INSTRUCTIONS

Introduction:

Would you like to discuss with others how social added value is or can be created in the food system of your city? With the RE-ADJUSTool you can jointly unpack and tackle the theme of social justice in urban food policies and initiatives in an accessible and co-creative way!

Components:

- 1 x instructions sheet
- 1 x playing board, consisting of 6 triangles
- 12 x definition cards: 4 per dimension
- 9 x evaluation question cards: 3 per dimension
- 9 x brainstorm question cards: 3 per dimension
- 1 x reflection & commitment (R&C) sheet
- 1 x personal notes sheet per person
- 9 x discussion notes sheets, or own note material

Provide yourself:

- 3 x markers: yellow, green & pink
- 1 x pen per person

Summary:

The RE-ADJUSTool distinguishes 3 dimensions when it comes to social justice: economic redistribution, cultural recognition and political representation. Each dimension is divided into 4 aspects. Descriptions of these aspects can be found on the 12 definition cards. By answering a number of questions about these aspects, you will discover during the game what it takes to build a more fair, humane and inclusive food system in your city.

The RE-ADJUSTool is played with 4 to 8 participants. Bring together stakeholders from different backgrounds, organisations and initiatives who are concerned with food and well-being in your city. It is advised to reserve approximately 3.5 hours for a full game. You can also divide the game into 3 sessions of 1 to 1.5 hours, each session focussing on a different dimension.

How to play:

Game preparation:

1. Compile the playing board by arranging the 6 triangles in such a way that you create a larger triangle with a pie-shaped diagram in the middle, as demonstrated in the example.
2. Position the definition cards around the playing board. Make sure that the icons on the cards match the icons on the board.
3. Determine the objective of the game:
 - Evaluation: Choose this objective if you would like to screen and improve your city's current food policies in terms of social justice.
 - Brainstorm: Choose this objective if you would like to brainstorm about what social food initiatives and -policy actions are needed in your city in the future.
4. Place the corresponding 9 question cards in stacks of 3 (question 1 on top) around the corners of the playing board, as demonstrated in the example.
5. Give each participant a personal notes sheet and a pen.
6. Make a short introduction round. Start with the participant who most recently handpicked something to eat from a plant, bush or tree. Answer the questions below. The person to the right of the speaker takes notes on the R&C sheet.
 - What is your favourite thing to eat straight from the source?
 - In what ways is your department, organisation or initiative trying to create social added value in the urban food system?
 - What stakeholders are missing at the table today?

Game rounds:

7. The participant who most recently cooked a meal for someone outside their household may start and receives the R&C sheet. The turn and the R&C sheet then rotate clockwise.
8. When it is your turn, you are the facilitator. Take the next question card from the pile, read it to the group and guide the discussion. The person on your right takes notes on a blank discussion notes sheet. The facilitator instructions on the R&C sheet provide a step-by-step guide of what to do in your turn.
9. In total, there are 3 game rounds, each consisting of 3 turns (1 question card per turn). Each game round focuses on one dimension of social justice:
 - Economic redistribution: about access to resources & pursuing fairness
 - Cultural recognition: about access to opportunities & celebrating diversity
 - Political representation: about access to structures & practicing democracy
10. The first two cards of each dimension contain discussion questions. The third and final question card invites you to give points. The four aspects of the dimension are to be assessed or prioritised (depending on the objective).
 - First, note down in silence the scores you would give in the mini diagram on your personal notes sheet.
 - Then explain to each other why you have given those scores and agree on 4 collective scores together.
 - Visualise these collective scores in the diagram on the playing board by colouring 0, 1, 2 or 3 areas for each aspect with the corresponding colour marker.

End of the game:

11. When you have finished all three rounds, have a final look at the diagram and R&C sheet and add any missing details. Discuss and confirm possible next steps.
12. Finally, take turns answering the last question on the R&C sheet (lessons).
13. Give yourself a big applause and do stick around to chat some more!

REFLECTION & COMMITMENT

at the start of the game

Who is present today?

Write down the participants' names and affiliations below.

What stakeholders are missing today?

Write down the organisations, groups or persons below.

Try to keep their interests and concerns in mind during today's discussions and think about ways to involve these stakeholders in a later stage!

Facilitator instructions: Is it your turn? In 10-20 minutes...

1. Take the next question card from the pile and read it to the group.
2. Hand out the 4 definition cards of the corresponding dimension to your fellow participants, starting with the person on your left.
3. Give the participants 2 minutes to think about the question(s) and write down their thoughts in silence.
4. Give each participant the opportunity to briefly respond to the question(s), either for the specific definition card they are holding or the dimension in general, starting with the person on your left. Other participants may comment.
5. Moderate the discussion. No worries, the neighbour on your right will take notes. It is your job to pay close attention to any potential to-do's and key-words that are mentioned and to write them down on the other side of this sheet. Keep directing the conversation to the question(s) and dimension on your card.
6. Together with your neighbour, summarise the discussion based on your notes. Ask the group if you have forgotten anything.
7. Your turn is over. Place the card and your neighbour's notes open on the table and give the R&C sheet to the person on your left.

during the game

Lessons:

When you have finished all question cards on the table, have another look at this sheet and add any final thoughts. Finish with a quick tour-de-table in which every participant shares an insight or takeaway from today's session. Summarise the lessons below.

at the end of the game

RE-ADJUSTool

Date: ___/___/___ City: _____

To-do's?

Whether you are evaluating or brainstorming, small tasks or promising ideas are likely to come up. However, when these proposals are not written down and made concrete, people will feel less responsible to take up these to-dos. But not today! Write down your plans below and ask your fellow participants who is willing to commit and who else needs to be involved. Try to be as specific as possible, and note, beneficiaries can also be initiators or partners!

What?	For whom? beneficiaries	By whom? initiators	With whom? partners	When?

Key-words:

Here you can jot down all relevant and recurring themes and concepts that reflect how social added value is or could be created within the food system of your city. Keep it brief and neat, and remember to leave some space for your fellow participants!

